

Principal's Leadership Style Based on Path-Goal Theory: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The importance of the principal's leadership style based on the Path-Goal Theory is interesting to study, and this paper examines the principal's leadership style based on the Path-Goal Theory in achieving educational goals in schools. There are several articles on reviews of leadership styles based on Path-Goal Theory that can be found. This review aims to find out the principal's leadership style based on path-goal theory in achieving educational goals in schools. Based on the literature review results, we found a significant relationship between the principal's leadership style based on Path-Goal Theory in achieving educational goals in schools, which could be seen from the increase in teacher performance and teacher job satisfaction in school administration staff. The article review results showed a significant correlation between the principal's leadership style based on the directive, supportive, participatory, and achievement-oriented leadership style on the level of performance and job satisfaction of teachers and administrative staff in schools. This is not underestimated from the influence of the principal's leadership style based on PathGoal Theory in directing and motivating his followers in achieving educational goals at school.

KEYWORDS: Leadership Style, Path-Goal Theory, Principal, School, Teachers' Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Background of this Article

The current era of globalization is faced with various rapid advances in the field of Science and Technology (Science and Technology), socio-cultural, economic, political, and one of them in the field of education. Education includes the means to develop potential in each individual. Then a quality education is needed. Quality education is strongly influenced by the quality of education. According to [1], the quality of education is the satisfaction of recipients of educational services to educational services. The quality of education in Indonesia has recently experienced a major challenge, where the covid-19 pandemic is an unavoidable challenge in Indonesia's current education system. So this phenomenon will directly affect the decline in the quality of education in an educational institution and no exception to the quality of Indonesian education as a whole. Indonesia's current quality of education is based on UNESCO's Global Education Monitoring Report 2020. This year's Global Education Monitoring Report noted that the gap in the literacy rate of adults with disabilities in Indonesia reached 41%. On the other hand, the level of attendance of secondary education students (age 15 years) in Indonesia has increased, although its development is still under the terms of achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals that have been agreed upon by United Nations member states in 2015. The quality of education will be directly proportional to the quality of learners. The quality of learners plays an important role in improving the quality of education in an educational institution itself. The quality of learners can be achieved through the achievement of teacher success in conducting learning activities, and guiding and directing the learners. According to [2], a teacher is someone who provides knowledge to students or professionals who can make their students plan, analyze and conclude the problems faced. Teachers in managing classroom learning that has an impact on the advancement of the quality of education in an educational institution are influenced by the commitment of the principal as the leader of the educational institution. According to [3], the leadership of the principal is the ability of the principal to move, direct, guide, protect, set an example, give encouragement and provide assistance to human resources in one school so that it can be used to the maximum.

Path-Goal Theory Leadership

There are four types of path-goal theory leadership styles: (1) directive leadership style, (2) supportive leadership style, (3) participative leadership style, and (4) achievement-oriented leadership style [4]. The directive leadership tells subordinates what is expected of them, provides specific guidelines, asks followers to follow rules and procedures, time, and coordinate their work.

Supportive leadership is leadership that shows the friendliness of a leader, is easy to meet, and shows an attitude of paying attention to his subordinates. Participative leadership is a leadership style in which they expect their suggestions and ideas before making a decision. Achievement-oriented leadership is a leadership style in which the leader sets challenging goals and expects subordinates to perform as much as possible and constantly seeks the development of achievements in achieving those goals [5].

The form of path-goal theory leadership is based on the satisfaction of the performance of its followers. According to this theory, a leader can be accepted by his or her co-author at the level that is reviewed by them as a source of satisfaction at that time or in the future. The behavior of the patient will give you a long motivation. Make the user feel the need for satisfaction in achieving effective performance, providing the learning, direction, support, and rewards needed for ineffective performance. This theory is seen to apply to leaders who choose a particular behavior that best suits the needs of members and the work environment so that they can guide members well through their ways of obtaining desired goals [4].

Importance and Gap of Literature Review

Many theories suggest different leadership styles. In this study, the authors focused on path-goal theory leadership. [6] identifying a path-goal theory leadership style that could be practiced to motivate followers to achieve goals. The idea of this path-goal theory is that motivation plays an important role in how supervisors and followers interact, based on those interactions so that success can be achieved in an organization [7]. So through this review journal, I will examine more in-depth path-goal theory leadership in schools, to add to the development of new theories about path-goal theory leadership in schools, because so far the same research has only focused on companies, course places, government, shops, hospitals, and colleges, but there is still very little research in schools. That's why I'm very interested in doing this research.

METHODS

This literature review focuses on the principal's leadership style based on path-goal theory. Integrative review methodologies are used to enable the inclusion of a wide range of theoretical and empirical literature. The review process is taken from relevant literature using transparent and reproducible search methods, and the data obtained is analyzed and synthesized. The review process begins with the search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with the keyword: "Principal's Leadership Style Based on Path-Goal Theory", which the principal does. Searches ranged from 2014 to 2022 and identified a total of 6.250 studies and articles on Asia and Africa.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Type

Research designs used in this scientific research are quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods.

2. Type of Intervention

The main study in scientific research is the leadership style of the principal based on path-goal theory. Journals that fit the criteria of inclusion and themed path-goal theory leadership style and the principal are further reviewed. The criteria of the journal selected for review are journals themed on path-goal theory leadership styles and principal. The inclusion criteria for this article are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Criteria for Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion
1. Path-Goal Theory Leadership	1. Leadership Style
2. Principal Leadership	2. Company/Shops/Hospitals/College
3. School	3. College Leaders
4. Teacher	4. Dissertation/Thesis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

This section reports the results of the reviewed article. The results of the analysis showed that most of the articles focused on PathGoal Theory leadership. But most of the article reviews do have not much to discuss the principals of leadership based on the Path-Goal Theory. The most article reviews only discuss Path-Goal Theory leadership only in the scope of companies, hospitals, shops, and colleges. While the article review at the school level is still limited and not much. But based on the results of the review that I found in the review of the article there is a significant relationship between the head of the school based on PathGoal Theory and the performance of his followers in achieving organizational or institutional goals. The results of journal research studies from different countries can be explained in the following table.

Table 2. Results of Literature Review

No	Title	Author(s) and Year	Type of Organization	N	Country	Method	Result
1	Principal Leadership Styles and Teacher Job Performance: Viewpoint of Middle Management	Saleem et al. (2020) [8]	School	253 middle management personnel	China	Empirical research	This research was conducted in a nonWestern culture, where directive leadership is beneficial for encouraging teacher job performance
2	Relationship between Principals' Leadership Styles and Secondary School Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Nandi South District, Kenya	Kiboss and Jemiryott (2014) [9]	School	138 respondents	Kenya	Ex-post facto research	The study also established that the dominant leadership style in Nandi South District was Democratic leadership style and that most teachers were satisfied with their jobs in relation to the leadership style in place.
3	Principals' Leadership Style and Staff Job Performance in Selected Secondary Schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria	Wilson (2017) [10]	School	210 questionnaires	Nigeria	Descriptive survey design	The findings proved that the principals face leadership challenges in the discharge of their administrative functions in the schools. Upon the findings, the study recommended that the principals should adopt the needed leadership style in their school to enhance staff job performance

4	Relationship between School Heads' Leadership Styles and Acceptance of Leader as moderated by Stress: testing path-goal theory in an educational setting	Saleem and Noshaba (2021) [11]	School	400 teachers	Pakistan	Quantitative research	Leadership Styles (directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented) were positively and significantly correlated with acceptance of the leader.
5	Relationship between Leadership Styles of School Heads and their Teachers' Job Satisfaction as Moderated by Locus of Control and Task Structure	Naureen et al. (2015) [12]	School	500 teachers	Pakistan	Quantitative research	Findings indicated that there was a direct relationship between all the leadership styles and job satisfaction. Task structure only affected the relation between achievement-oriented style and job satisfaction.
6	Path-Goal Leadership Effectiveness Perception In Selected Private Secondary Schools In Rivers State	Nzeneri (2020) [13]	School	1.292 teachers	Nigeria	descriptive and survey design	The path-goal theory has implications for education in the sense that leaders' success depends on / her relationship with the workers, ability to adapt leadership styles i.e. directive, supportive, achievement-oriented and participative which promotes empowerment and encourages outstanding workers' performance.
7	Effect of Principals' Leadership Styles on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kieni West Sub-County	Wachira et al. (2017) [14]	School	22 principals and 262 teachers	Kenya	Descriptive survey research	The researcher also concludes that supportive leadership style affects teachers' performance; in schools where the principal practices supportive leadership style, there is improved teacher performance.

8	A Comparative Study of Teachers' Perceptions Towards Principals' Leadership Behaviors at Jeyang And Hkachyang Middle Schools in Laiza, Kachin State, Myanmar	Nnye and Vinitwatanak hun (2019) [15]	97 teachers	Myanmar	Quantitative and comparative study	Based on the data analysis, teachers in Jiang Middle School perceived its principal's leadership behavior as directive most often and as achievement-oriented less often than other behaviors.
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2. Discussion

Path-goal theory is divided into indicators of effective leadership, namely participatory leadership, directive, supportive, and achievement orientation. [6] in which there are four types of leadership styles, namely: (1) directive leadership style, (2) supportive leadership style, (3) participatory leadership style, and (4) achievement-oriented leadership style. Directive leadership and achievement orientation are the most widely accepted leadership by followers. According to [8], as the results of the review, Path-Goal leadership influences the performance of its followers, namely where directive leadership is very useful to encourage teacher job performance in schools. The leadership directive here gives guidelines, allowing subordinates to know what to expect from their followers, set performance standards for their followers, and behavior control when performance standards are not met. Leaders wisely reward and sanction discipline. Achievement-oriented leadership sets challenging goals and encourages followers to achieve their best performance. Leaders believe that their followers are responsible enough to achieve challenging goals. This style is the same as the view of goal-setting theory. [9] where research adopted that the Path-Goal Theory affects the performance, satisfaction, and motivation of followers, namely where the principal has a good leadership style, thus impacting the good school atmosphere and teacher satisfaction increases. [11] where leadership styles (directive, supportive, participatory and achievement-oriented) have a positive and significant relationship to the acceptance of leaders. [12] describe a direct relationship between all leadership styles to the job satisfaction of their followers, but the task structurally only affects the relationship between performance-oriented style and job satisfaction. [14] explained that the supportive leadership style affects the performance of the teacher's work in the school, this is where the principal not only submits the assignment to the teacher and receives the results, but the principal cooperates with the teacher so that the teacher feels supported by the principal. [15] perception of teachers in Jeyang high school, Myanmar considers that the leadership style of the headmaster directive is most often done, while the performance-oriented leadership style is still rare. The success of the principal's leadership based on path-goal theory depends on how the principal can establish good relationships with his followers. [13] explains that the success of leaders depends on how leaders make relationships with workers, where they can be directive, supportive, participatory, and achievement-oriented in promoting, empowering, and supporting the performance of their followers to be extraordinary. The leadership of the principal affects the satisfaction of teachers in the school and has an impact on the satisfaction of school administration personnel. [10] in his study explained that bringing the leadership style of principals based on Path-Goal Theory has an impact on the work of administrative employees, to achieve school goals.

CONCLUSION

In general, it can be concluded that the principal's leadership style based on Path-Goal Theory has a positive effect between the principal and his followers in this case the teachers and administrative staff in the school. The application of Path-Goal Theory becomes a viable solution to the challenges of leadership and followers in an educational institution. The principal's leadership behavior is based on Path-Goal Theory where the directive, supportive, participatory leadership style, and achievement orientation greatly affect the satisfaction, motivation, performance, and work expectations of teachers in schools so that school goals can be achieved properly. However, the principal's directive leadership style has a significant effect on teacher job satisfaction, because when the principal conveys or orders his followers to carry out their duties with detailed explanations to their followers, it directly has an impact on increasing teacher job satisfaction in schools. Like any other study, this review has limitations. First, article reviews are only in Indonesian and English so other research is not reviewed due to the author's limitations. Second, the scope of the article

reviewed is still very limited, in this article the scope is only limited to research conducted in several countries in the African continent and some countries in the Asian continent, while the variation of research results in African and Asian countries reviewed is still very minimal. The last limitation is that no single measure can be compared between studies. This review is still minimal, so further studies on principal leadership based on Path-Goal Theory need to be done.

REFERENCES

1. Triatna, C., *Organizational behavior in education*. 2015, Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
2. Djamarah and Zain, *Teaching and learning strategies*. 2015, Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
3. Wahjosumidjo, *Principal leadership: a theoretical review and its problems*. 2005, Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
4. Northouse, P.G., *Leadership: Theory and practice*. 2021: Sage publications.
5. House, R.J. and T.R. Mitchell, *Path-goal theory of leadership*. 1975: p. 75-67.
6. House, R.J., *A path goal theory of leader effectiveness*. *Administrative science quarterly*, 1971: p. 321-339.
7. House, R.J., *Path-goal theory of leadership: Lessons, legacy, and a reformulated theory*. *The leadership quarterly*, 1996. 7(3): p. 323-352.
8. Saleem, A., et al., *Principal leadership styles and teacher job performance: Viewpoint of middle management*. *Sustainability*, 2020. 12(8): p. 3390.
9. Kiboss, J.K. and H.K.S. Jemiryott, *Relationship between principals' leadership styles and secondary school teachers' job satisfaction in Nandi South District, Kenya*. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 2014. 3(2): p. 493-509.
10. Wilson, G., *Principals' leadership style and staff job performance in selected secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria*. *African Research Review*, 2017. 11(3): p. 115-131.
11. Saleem, A. and A. Noshaba, *Relationship between school heads' leadership styles and acceptance of leader as moderated by stress: testing path goal theory in educational setting*. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Educational Studies*, 2021. 1(2): p. 44-63.
12. Naureen, G. and A. Noshaba, *Relationship between leadership styles of school heads and their teachers' job satisfaction as moderated by locus of control and task structure*. *Journal of Educational Research*, 2015. 18(2): p. 14.
13. NZENERI, N.E., *Path goal leadership effectiveness perception in selected private secondary schools in rivers state*. *International Journal of Institutional Leadership, Policy and Management*, 2020. 2(2): p. 348-268.
14. Wachira, F.M., M. Gitumu, and Z. Mbugua, *Effect of principals' leadership styles on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Kieni West Sub-County*. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2017. 6(8): p. 72-86.
15. Nnye, L. and W. Vinitwatanakhun, *A Comparative Study of Teachers' Perceptions Towards Principals' Leadership Behaviors at Jeyang and Hkachyang Middle Schools in Laiza, Kachin State, Myanmar*. *Scholar: Human Sciences*, 2019. 11(1): p. 181-181.

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